

and the final one with 0.2 mm. diameter was chosen. Moreover the length of capillary was such that a very steady and slow rate of flow could be attained.

Incidentally we come to the conclusion that the use of viscometer of the type B is open to serious error especially due to the temperature differences in its body. This has been discussed above. It was to avoid this source of error that the viscometer C was employed. In this case the whole body of the viscometer was directly in contact with the thermostat bath so that within experimental errors, at least this possible source of error was eliminated.

Jones and Talley (*loc. cit.*) have used a photo-electric cell to record the time automatically to avoid the errors arising out of the human factor. They, however, noted only the times of fall (in the Washburn Williams type of the viscometer). The above results show, however that under the conditions of the experiments this was not a source of error, at least, not to the extent of accounting for the observed erraticity of results for the time of rise.

The authors have tried to eliminate almost all the possible sources of error in the above series of experiments but yet it is puzzling to find the above-mentioned discrepancy in the times for rise while those for fall giving good readings.

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Received July 6, 1934.

On a New Type of Liquid-Liquid Junction.

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The presence of liquid junction potentials is a source of considerable difficulty in the accurate measurement of the *e.m.f.* of cells. The use of a saturated solution of potassium chloride or ammonium nitrate as the bridge liquid (Bjerrum, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, **53**, 428; Cumming and Abbegg, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1907, **13**, 17) does not always

completely eliminate the liquid junction potential (*cf.* *Scotchard, J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925 **47**, 696) whereas the method suggested by Bjerrum (*loc. cit.*) at best, eliminates the liquid potential only partially. Owing to their instability, the values of the junction potentials cannot be determined accurately by experimental methods. Weyl (*Dissert. Karlsruhe, 1905*), Lewis and Rupert (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **33**, 299), Cumming and Gilchrist (*Trans. Faraday Soc*, 1913, **9**, 174) and various other investigators have attempted to get reproducible and constant junction potentials in order that their values might be determined. But in almost every case it has been found that the observed *e.m.f.* fails to give a constant value and changes by several millivolts through "ageing" These fluctuations in the values of the junction potentials are mainly due to disturbances produced by diffusion effects.

In order to minimise the disturbing effects of diffusion, various types of junctions have been attempted. Bjerrum (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, **17**, 389) used finely divided sand as the medium where the two liquids were allowed to meet. Myers and Acree (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1913, **50**, 396) and Lewis, Brighton and Sebastian (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2245), have, however, shown that Bjerrum's method is not efficient. Lamb and Larson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 299) sought to reduce diffusion by using finely bored capillary tubing, but as has been shown by Cumming and Gilchrist (*loc. cit.*) the procedure fails to give accurate values. Attempts towards decreasing the interfacial area of the junction by mechanical means such as plugging the ends of connecting tubes by rolls of filter paper, cotton wool or cones of wood and the use of glass taps without grease have all failed to give satisfactory reproducible values (*cf.* *Glasstone, "Electrochemistry of solutions,"* p. 285).

Guggenheim (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1315) has used a special type of liquid junction. The concentrations of the two solutions A and B, forming the liquid junction, were so adjusted that they gradually varied from 100% of A and 0% of B at one end to 100% of B and 0% of A at the other end. A continuous mixture junction of gradual concentration gradient was thereby obtained. Guggenheim considers such a bridge contact, superior to the free diffusion liquid junction. Recent investigation by Ferguson, Valentine and Hitchin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1279) have shown that the results with the types of junction used by Guggenheim

are not so satisfactory as those obtained by using a junction of the free diffusion type.

The flowing junction introduced by Lamb and Larson (*loc. cit.*) goes a long way towards giving reproducible junction potentials, where diffusion disturbances are considerably eliminated by constant renewal of the contact surface. Robert and Fenwick (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2788) by using a special type of flowing junction have obtained values which are in accordance with the Lewis and Sargent formula. It has however, been shown recently by Ferguson (*loc. cit.*) that the potential of the flowing junction is dependent on the rate of flow and attains a constant value only when rate of the flow is rapid. Moreover, in the flowing junction, the two solutions are always in contact and this vitiates reproducibility as the potential difference is not restricted to the contact interface, but communicates to certain distance, within the bulk of the solutions in the half cells, as has been clearly demonstrated by Ferguson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

It is well known that the diffusion of a dissolved solid follows Fick's equation,

$$ds = -D \cdot q \cdot \frac{dc}{dx} \cdot dt$$

where ds , the quantity diffused is directly proportional to q , the cross section, dt , the time and dc/dx , the concentration gradient. Most of the previous attempts summarised above have been directed towards minimising diffusion effects by a decrease of q , the interfacial area of the junction, whilst Guggenheim's constant mixture junction aims at lowering dc/dx , the concentration gradient at the contact interface. It is evident, however, that in addition to the above two factors a decrease in the value of dt , the time of contact of the two solutions forming the junction, should also contribute towards diminished diffusion. It was, therefore, hoped that by lowering the time of contact sufficiently, the ageing effect of the liquid junction would be largely eliminated. Keeping the above point in view, a type of junction has been devised where, in addition to a small interfacial area of the junction, the time of contact is reduced to a minimum by allowing the solutions to come in contact only momentarily. Using the junction described below, a series of determinations of the junction potentials have been

carried out and it has been found that it is capable of giving fairly constant and reproducible values.

FIG. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. 1. The cell was made up of two electrode vessels having no detachable side-tubes A and B. These were made out of thin walled glass tubings the bore of the tubings having a diameter of 1 mm. By manipulation of the tap T, a full grown drop was formed at the tip of A and kept suspended there. With the help of the capillary tap T' and the screw-clip S, a drop could be gradually formed at the end of the tip B. The ends of the tips A and B were paraffined and the distance between them was so adjusted that the drop at the end of the tip B, when nearly fully formed, would come into contact with the drop previously suspended at the end of a tip A, and at the next instant both the drops would detach from the tips and fall down. Thus for the very short period the two drops were in contact, the electrical circuit was completed through the potentiometer, previously kept ready for measurement by depression of the X-key. By forming several pairs of drops by repetition of the above process, potentiometer could be easily made to give the exact value of the *e.m.f.* of the cell. It is important that both the drops detach immediately after they have come in contact with the another.

In order to test the reproducibility of *e.m.f.* of cells with the above type of junctions, a series of Hg | Hg₂Cl₂ and Ag | AgCl cells with different junction solutions were set up and their values measured. The materials employed for the setting up of these cells were very carefully purified. The calomel employed was prepared by the electrolytic method recommended by Hulett and Lipscombe (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 22). The silver chloride electrode was prepared according to the method of Carmody (*ibid.*, 1929, 51, 2901). To exclude the action of light during measurements the Ag | AgCl cell was set up in electrode vessels which were coated with black Japan on the outside. The thermostat was run at 25° and the temperature was constant to $\pm 0.02^\circ$. The heater in the thermostat was screened to prevent any electrical leakage. The potentiometer used was a Tinsley one and was capable of giving readings to a hundredth of a millivolt. The experimental values are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

No.	Cell.	<i>e.m.f.</i> in millivolts.		
		Observed with drop contact.	Obtained by previous authors.	
1.	Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ , 0.1N-KCl 0.1N-HCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	28.16	27.8	Lewis Brighton and Sebastian
			26.78	Mc Innes and Yeh.
2.	Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ , 0.01N-KCl 0.01N-HCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	27.53	27.2	L. B. and S.
3.	Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ , 0.0N-KCl 0.01N-KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	52.64	52.9	Fales and Mudge
4.	Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ , 0.1N-KCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	89.42	91.6	Do
5.	Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ , 1.0N-KCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	37.96	38.7	Do
6.	Ag AgCl, 0.1N-HCl 0.01N-HCl, AgCl Ag	91.80	92.37	Ferguson and co-workers
7.	Ag AgCl, 0.05N-KCl 0.05N-KCl, AgCl Ag	53.38	53.57	Mc. Innes and Parker
8.	Ag AgCl, 0.1N-KCl 0.01N-KCl, AgCl Ag	53.24	54.00	Do
9.	Ag AgCl, 0.1N-HCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	42.52	44.76	Ferguson and co-workers
10.	Ag AgCl, 0.01N-HCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	96.60	99.16	Do

The reproducibility was observed in the above measurements to be within a few hundredth of a millivolt with the same setting but with different settings it rose to a few tenths. The values in the cells 1 and 2 involving a liquid junction potential between KCl/HCl are found to be distinctly higher than those given in literature.

whereas the *e.m.f.* values of the concentration cells 3, 6, 7 and 8 are practically the same as given by previous investigators. It might be mentioned that the *e.m.f.* of concentration cells are independent of the nature of the liquid junction. The values with the saturated calomel electrodes as in cells 4, 5, 9 and 10 were, however, found to be somewhat lower than the values given in the literature.

It was desired to compare the variations with time of the values obtained with this drop contact method with those obtained on the same cell by the continuous mixture type of junction (*cf.* Guggenheim) and the free diffusion type (*cf.* Ferguson *loc cit.*). The cell examined was

The continuous mixture was set up in N-tube filled with sand. For the free diffusion type of junction, a N-tube with a stop-cock (9 mm. bore) in the limb was used. The data obtained are given in Table II and the curves are plotted in Fig. 2

FIG 2.

I Const. mixture type. II. From diff. type. III Drop contact technique

TABLE II.

Time.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed in millivolts with		
	Free diffusion type. (<i>cf.</i> curve I)	Cont. mixture type. (<i>cf.</i> curve II)	Drop contact. (<i>cf.</i> curve III)
0	27.82	28.21	28.32
1 hr.	27.67	27.88	28.30
2	27.48	27.65	28.23
4	27.46	27.47	28.28
8	27.36	27.29	29.23

It is apparent from curve III in Fig. 2, that the characteristic initial fall in *e.m.f.* values is practically absent, whereas it is present in curves I and II. Incidentally it also proves the superiority of the free diffusion type of liquid junction over the continuous mixture type, agreeing with the observation of Ferguson and co-workers, as has been mentioned before.

TABLE III.

No.	Cell.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed in millivolts by		
		Free diffusion type.	Drop contact.	Difference in millivolts.
1.	Ag AgCl, 0.1N-HCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	41.04	42.67	1.63
2.	Ag AgCl, 0.01N-HCl Sat. KCl, Hg ₂ Cl ₂ Hg	95.08	96.73	1.65

In Table III are given the *e.m.f.* values of two cells with calomel saturated KCl as one of their half cells, with the free diffusion and drop contact type of junctions. As there exists a definite difference of about 1.6 millivolt in both the cells between the two types of junctions, it is evident that saturated KCl solutions do not completely eliminate the liquid junction potentials as has also been observed by Scatchard (*loc. cit.*) and more recently by Ferguson and co-workers.

It is well known that there is a decrease in the *e. m. f.* of the 0.1M and 1M-KCl calomel cells when used in conjunction with a saturated KCl bridge. Richards and Archibald (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 40, 385) attributed this to the formation of a complex mercuric ion by the interaction of the alkali chloride and the calomel. But Fales and Mudge (*loc. cit.*) have definitely shown that this is due to the diffusion of the concentrated solution of KCl from the bridge

into the half cells. In the drop contact technique developed above, it is evident that the half cells are free from any such deteriorations. The ageing effect with time is also absent. Large quantities of cell liquids, as in the case of flowing junctions, are also unnecessary. The method may also be of great value in the case of *c. m. f.* measurements with colloidal solutions, where the bridge liquid often introduces further complications by coagulation of the colloids at the tips of the connecting tubes.

In conclusion, the author wishes to express his thanks to Dr. P. B. Ganguly, D.Sc. for his kind interest in this work.

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Received October 1^o, 1934.

A Note on the Reduction of Selenium Dioxide by Carbon Monoxide.

BY EDWARD BARNES.

Carbon monoxide from formate was dried over P_2O_5 and freed from traces of oxygen by passing over red hot copper gauze and then granulated potassium hydroxide. Selenium dioxide was sublimed into the vessels (cleansed by chromic, nitric acid mixture) in a dry stream of oxygen with a little NO_2 (oxygen carrier). Carbon monoxide was then introduced by repeated evacuation. With sealed glass tubes no reduction had taken place after several days' exposure to tropical sunlight. With a quartz vessel no reduction was brought about by several hours' exposure to intense radiation from a quartz mercury lamp. By slowly heating sealed glass tubes in an electrical heater with a mica window slight reduction was observed to occur at about 250° . By careful heating, however, in a quartz vessel it was found that selenium dioxide could be sublimed unchanged in carbon monoxide. By continually subliming a quantity of selenium dioxide from one side of a vessel to the other in a stream of carbon monoxide by strong heating with a bare gas flame only 17.2 mg. of selenium was separated after 40 minutes and only 16 mg. of CO was collected in the absorption tube.

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Received September 1, 1934.